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Effect of Foliar Iodine Application on Some Yield Parameters and Biofortification Level in Red and White Cabbage Cultivars

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Abstract

Background and aim: Iodine deficiency in plant foods, which occurs due to iodine deficiency in soils, is among the most important problems in human nutrition and health worldwide. Iodine biofortification applied from various sources according to plant species and varieties is among the most suitable options to increase iodine content in plant foods. In this study, it was aimed to increase the iodine content of red and white cabbage plants with foliar iodine solutions and to determine the effects on the plant.

Materials and methods: In the study conducted under field conditions, increasing doses of iodine were applied to red and white cabbage plants foliarly at certain developmental stages. Product parameters and iodine contents of cabbage plants at harvest stage were analyzed.

Results: Foliar iodine applications to red and white cabbage plants increased iodine content in both varieties. Significant changes were determined in fresh and marketable weight and diameter of white cabbage plants due to the dose effect, and the optimum foliar application level was determined as 0.2 mg L⁻¹ iodine. White cabbage plants contained higher levels of iodine than red cabbage plants and responded better to foliar iodine applications. Fresh and marketable weight, length and diameter values were higher in white cabbage plants.

Conclusion: The results showed that foliar iodine applications were successful in iodine biofortification in white cabbage plants, but different iodine levels in foliar applications and soil application options should be evaluated in red cabbage plants.

Keywords: *Biofortification, Iodine, Foliar application, Cabbage varieties*

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Introduction

Micronutrient deficiencies in the soil limit crop productivity and the nutritional quality of food, which in turn affects nutrition and human health. Micronutrient deficiencies in humans mainly result from low concentrations and low availabilities of micronutrients in daily diets [1]. This can lead to growth problems, weak immune systems and mental development problems, especially in children. Iodine was the first trace element recognized as being essential for humans essential for humans [2] and plays a critical role in various functions of the body such as thyroid function, brain development, immune system, cardiovascular health, metabolism and regulation of energy levels. Optimal dietary iodine intakes for healthy adults are 150–250 µg/d [3]. Iodine deficiency diseases are a serious health problem worldwide, estimated to affect ~35 % of the world's population and placing significant social and economic pressure on developing countries [4]. For these reasons, adequate iodine intake is essential for maintaining a healthy life. Iodine is involved in the cognitive abilities in humans and in reducing the risk of certain types of cancer [5]. Iodine deficiency can lead to various health problems, so it is important to consume iodine-containing foods with a balanced diet plan.

All the nutrients consumed by humans are derived from the soil-plant system. A new approach to tackling the problem of micronutrient deficiency in human and animal diets has been to increase the concentration and bioavailability of micronutrients in the edible parts of plants through biofortification. This approach is sustainable, relatively low-cost and highly effective, and has particular applicability in poorer regions of the World [6], [7]. Plant biofortification is an important agricultural strategy used to increase the nutrient content of plants to promote healthy diets and combat nutrient deficiencies. Plant biofortification is defined as procedures aimed at increasing the content of certain elements, nutrient compounds and vitamins in plant yields in order to improve their biological quality and consequently improve the health of food consumers [8]. Agronomic biofortification is achieved through the application of micronutrient fertilizers such as iodine, zinc, molybdenum, selenium to the soil and/or foliar application directly to the leaves of the crop. Biofortification of different crop varieties offers a sustainable and long-term solution to provide people with micronutrient-rich crops [9].

Iodine biofortification refers to the process of increasing or enriching the iodine content of plants or animals. This process is an important strategy to increase the iodine intake of people living in iodine-deficient areas and reduce health problems associated with iodine deficiency. In addition to the use of iodised table salts, iodine biofortification of plant is one of the methods of iodine supply [10]. The iodine content of the cabbage plant, which is widely used in many countries around the world, is very important in human nutrition. Adequate iodine content of cabbage plants is important for people to get this important mineral.

Iodine is one of the least available elements, with only about 3 mg kg⁻¹ iodine is found in soils [11]. In the presence of iodine deficiency in the soil, foliar iodine application as a cultural practice increases the iodine uptake of the plant by enabling iodine absorption by the leaves of the plant. Foliar iodization can help meet public health and nutritional needs by increasing the iodine content of plants.

In iodine biofortification, iodine uptake and assimilation capacities of plants, application forms and doses may differ according to plant species. In this study, the effects of foliar application of iodine at different concentrations to red and white cabbage plants grown under field conditions on plant growth, product parameters and iodine contents were investigated.

Material and Methods

The experiment was conducted in experimental field. The physical and chemical analytical characteristics of the experimental soil were within the range of acceptable values for vegetable plants (Table 1).

Table 1. The analytical characteristics of the experimental soil before applications.

Parameters	
Texture	Loam
pH- H ₂ O (1:5 w/v)	7.58
CaCO ₃ , %	9.62
Organic matter, %	1.15
CEC, cmol kg ⁻¹	18.4
EC, dS m ⁻¹ 25°C	0.25
Total N, %	1.32
P (ex), mg kg ⁻¹	7.5
K (ex), mg kg ⁻¹	351
Ca (ex), mg kg ⁻¹	2880
Mg (ex), mg kg ⁻¹	423
Fe (ex), mg kg ⁻¹	88
Mn (ex), mg kg ⁻¹	74
Zn(ex), mg kg ⁻¹	5.2
Cu (ex), mg kg ⁻¹	2.4

According to the randomized block design, 50 ppm N (as of ammonium sulphate fertilizer, 21 % N), 30 ppm P (as triple super phosphate fertilizer, 44 % P₂O₅) and 50 ppm K (as potassium sulphate fertilizer, 46 % K₂O) were applied as basic fertilizer to the experimental plots prepared in 2 x 3 m dimensions with 5 replications before the seedlings were transplanted into the soil.

From the healthy red and white cabbage seedlings germinated in germination crates, 6 of them were transplanted to each plot and regular irrigation maintenance and phenological observations were made until the harvest period.

Foliar iodine applications were made 4 times at 7-day intervals to red and white cabbage plants at the umbilical (wrapping) stage. Foliar iodine application doses were prepared from KI as shown below and commercial foliar fertilizer adhesive preparations were added to the Iodien solutions between applications to increase foliar adhesion.

Table 2. Iodine Levels Applied to Cabbage Plants

Applications	Iodine, mg L ⁻¹
1.	0 (Control)
2.	0.05
3.	0.10
4.	0.20
5.	0.40
6.	0.80

Cabbage plants that reached harvest maturity at the end of 4 months were harvested by cutting from the soil surface and weighed together with all the leaves to determine the total weight and weighed again after the leaves that were not used for consumption were removed to determine the marketable weight. Cabbage plants were cut transversely and longitudinally and their length and diameter were determined.

Harvested cabbage plants were sampled by longitudinal section and prepared for analysis by

washing, drying and grinding. The iodine content of the dried and ground plant samples was determined as described by [12].

The analysis of variance of the findings obtained in the greenhouse experiment carried out according to the random blocks experimental design with 5 replicates was analysed using SPSS software.

Results

The effects of foliar iodine applications on fresh weight, marketable weight, plant head diameter and iodine content in white cabbage plants and on iodine content in red cabbage plants were statistically significant. The effects of foliar iodine applications on head length of cabbage plants were not significant. The standard deviation values of the other parameters except iodine content of the plant due to foliar iodine applications were higher in white cabbage plants (Table 3).

Table 3. Effects of foliar iodine applications on some yield parameters and iodine contents of red and white cabbage cultivars

Statistics	Fresh weight, g		Marketable weight, g		Length, cm		Diameter, cm		Iodine content, mg kg ⁻¹ dry w.	
	Red cabbage	White cabbage	Red cabbage	White cabbage	Red cabbage	White cabbage	Red cabbage	White cabbage	Red cabbage	White cabbage
Std. Deviation	1003,0	2897,3	541,0	1945,0	1,981	4,396	1,841	3,372	13,874	1,361
Variance	0,595	0,005*	0,995	0,049*	0,547	0,077	0,898	0,042*	0,013*	0,001*
Minimum	1600,00	1400,00	750,00	1000,00	11,30	13,50	13,00	14,00	2,60	0,68
Maximum	6100,00	12500,00	3200,00	9050,00	21,10	32,50	22,00	27,00	69,93	5,66

Although iodine element is not an absolutely essential plant nutrient, it had a positive effect on plant growth and crop yield by increasing fresh weight and diameter values of white cabbage plants at 0.2 mg L⁻¹ application level. Foliar iodine applications had a decreasing effect on fresh weight and marketable weight values in white cabbage plants at 0.4-0.8 mg L⁻¹ application levels. In red cabbage plants, fresh and marketable weight values did not show significant changes depending on iodine applications. Fresh and marketable weight values were higher in white cabbage plants at all iodine application levels (Figure 1, Figure 2).

Figure 1. Effect of foliar iodine applications on fresh weight of red and white cabbage cultivars

Figure 2. Effect of foliar iodine applications on marketable weight of red and white cabbage cultivars

The effect of foliar iodine applications on the head length value of cabbage plants was not significant. Although the length value showed a decrease in white cabbage plants and a partial increase in red cabbage plants at 0.4-0.8 mg L⁻¹ iodine application levels, the results were not significant. The length value was higher in white cabbage plants at all iodine treatment levels (Figure 3). The diameter value of cabbage plant was highest at 0.2 mg L⁻¹ iodine treatment level. At higher iodine application levels (0.4-0.8 mg L⁻¹), the diameter value of white cabbage plants decreased. There was no significant change in the diameter value of red cabbage plants due to iodine treatments. At all iodine application levels, the diameter value was higher in white cabbage plants (Figure 4).

Figure 3. Effect of foliar iodine applications on length of red and white cabbage cultivars

Figure 4. Effect of foliar iodine applications on diameter of red and white cabbage cultivars

The iodine content of red and white cabbage plants increased due to foliar iodine applications. The increase in iodine coverage was approximately 6 times higher in white cabbage plants. The increase in iodine content of red cabbage plants was found to be relatively low (Figure 5). This indicates that white cabbage plants have higher foliar absorption capacity due to iodine applications and respond more strongly to iodine biofortification.

Figure 5. Effect of foliar iodine applications on iodine content of red and white cabbage cultivars

Discussion

Studies to date have reported that soil and foliar iodine applications can have different effects on plant growth depending on the application dose, plant species and cultivars. Foliar iodine applications caused biomass loss in maize [13] and tomato plants [14], but increased biomass in soybean [13] and Chinese cabbage [15]. In conclusion, genotype effect of iodine treatment on vegetative growth, developmental parameters and iodine enrichment level of cabbage cultivars was dominant and white cabbage plants responded more effectively to iodine biofortification.

The effect of iodine, which is not an absolute essential nutrient, on physiological mechanisms in plants is not yet fully understood. In *Arabidopsis*, which is considered as a model plant, iodine application at low concentrations was found to increase biomass, provide early flowering stage and play a functional role in plant nutrition [16]. In addition, iodine applications in pepper plants were found to provide positive improvements in biomass increase, antioxidant activity and element concentration [17]. Both positive and negative results in the data obtained from the studies on this subject require detailed studies based on plant species and varieties and application dosage for iodine applications.

Conclusion

It was observed that iodine biofortification in cabbage plants was successfully achieved by foliar iodine applications, but this application did not give the expected results in red cabbage plants. Furthermore, although iodine is not considered as an absolutely essential nutrient for plants, foliar iodine applications resulted in significant changes in product parameters in white cabbage plants, whereas no or minimal changes were observed in red cabbage plants. It is thought that different doses and application options of iodine applications should be evaluated to overcome the relative low iodine absorption and assimilation in red cabbage plants due to varietal differences.

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Conflict of interests

The authors declare that there are no competing interests Conclusion.

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